

MEDICAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF THE DENTAL STATUS OF ELDERLY AND OLD AGE PATIENTS ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE

Aliyev T.,

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant
Department of Pediatric Dentistry
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Huseynova R.,

*Department of Therapeutic c Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Jalilova G.

*Department of Pediatrik Dentistry Assistant
Azerbaijan Medical University
Baku, Azerbaijan*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789252>

Abstract

Human health should be considered as a multifaceted concept that implies the physiological, psychological well-being and social adaptation of a person. In elderly and senile patients, the manifestation of many diseases of the organs and tissues of the mouth is associated both with the natural aging processes of the body and with the presence of diseases of the internal organs. There is no doubt that the combination of existing diseases reduces the quality of life of elderly and senile patients and contributes to their social isolation.

Keywords: gerontology, dentistry, quality of life, dental health, dental questionnaires

Over the past century, a steady trend of population aging has formed in the world. Some authors argue that this process is a consequence of a decrease in the birth rate, an increase in the death rate of people of working age and, as a result, an increase in the population of elderly and senile age [1]. Other scientists attribute the natural aging of the population to an increase in life expectancy, which was facilitated by the progress of science and reforms in the health care system, allowing early diagnosis and treatment of somatic diseases, which to this day are the main cause of death in the population. The health of organs and tissues of the mouth is an important part of human health as a whole, when this conceptual concept is considered not only as the absence of a particular disease, but rather as the presence of an optimally functioning organism, psychologically and socially adapted in society [3]. Dental care elderly and senile age has a number of features. In this category of patients, it is difficult to find preserved dentitions. Most teeth have previously been treated for caries and its complications. It is quite difficult to reliably determine whether a tooth is intact or not, since most of the remaining teeth at this age are covered with artificial crowns. It is in patients of the older age group that root caries prevails over crown caries and, according to a number of authors, the frequency of this pathology is about 80% [2]. Along with caries and its complications, the number of patients suffering from periodontal diseases also increases with age. At the same time, along with inflammatory forms caused by the presence of general somatic diseases, there is an increase in dystrophic forms associated with the development of involutive processes in an aging organism [1]. As a result of

the high prevalence of diseases of the organs and tissues of the mouth, by the age of 60, patients are missing up to half of all teeth, and further the process of tooth loss is aggravated [4, 5]. Conducted studies of the dental status of elderly and senile patients have shown that the frequency of complete absence of teeth is 28.9% in the elderly and 43.3% in the elderly [5, 6]. In elderly dentistry, the manifestation of many diseases of the organs and tissues of the mouth is associated with the presence of diseases of the internal organs. According to the literature data, diseases of the cardiovascular system occupy the first place in the structure of the incidence of elderly and senile people. This is followed by a group of oncological diseases, diseases of the nervous system, musculoskeletal system, gastrointestinal tract and respiratory organs [1]. The incidence of elderly and senile people has a number of significant features. One of them is polymorbidity - the presence of two or more long-term chronic diseases in a patient. Also, when providing medical care to the elderly, it is necessary to take into account their special psychological state and social status. Together, these factors quite often destroy constructive communication between a medical professional and an elderly patient, which is so necessary in the process of diagnosing, treating and rehabilitating patients of this age group in order to obtain a stable positive result. Partial or complete absence of teeth entails dissatisfaction with appearance, embarrassment when smiling, laughing or talking, inability to eat favorite foods, inability to taste, speak or swallow. All this significantly complicates the daily activities of a person, negatively affects social behavior and self-confidence

[7, 8]. There is no doubt that the combination of existing diseases, both dental and somatic, reduces the quality of life of elderly and senile patients and contributes to their social isolation. One of the main factors that determine the quality of life is persistent chronic pain. It negatively affects the emotional, physical and economic state of a person, disrupting the rhythm of his daily life. People are more likely to stay at home, avoid meetings with friends and family members, worry about their health status and constantly consult with doctors [3], as an autonomous anatomical structure associated with the body is very conditional. Proceeding from this provision, studies of assessing the state of dental health are based on subjective information - patient complaints and objective information - examination results, data from clinical and laboratory studies [2, 3, 7, 8]. Rarely evaluate indicators such as an open smile, free laughter, conversation, not overshadowed by bad breath, the ability to eat your favorite food in a public place. The relationship between dental health and possible insomnia, nausea, headache, and overweight is even less often assessed [7, 8]. An analysis of the state of dental health in terms of assessing the quality of life can help resolve many issues of organizing dental care for the elderly and senile population. By studying the criteria for assessing the quality of life, it is possible not only to improve oral health, but also to improve the quality of medical care and the level of well-being of people. A correctly selected questionnaire for assessing the quality of life will make it possible to accurately assess violations in the state of health of patients, more clearly present the essence of the clinical problem, determine a rational approach to treatment, and evaluate the results of work in terms of parameters that are at the junction of the scientific approach of a specialist and the subjective point of view of the patient.

[9]. People of elderly and senile age can be called a socially vulnerable group of the population. The main criteria determining social insecurity are a low level of monthly income, a restriction in the provision of social benefits in the provision of dental care, the impossibility of regular visits to the dentist as a result of the presence of general somatic diseases or territorial remoteness from the dental clinic. Therefore, during the period of demographic instability, medical care for people the elderly can and should be considered as one of the priority areas of the modern health care system.

Findings.

In the course of the study, it was found that older people who continue to work, live in families, have an average and high average monthly income, lead an active lifestyle, initially had higher quality of life indicators than people who do not work, with low incomes, lonely and forced to lead a passive lifestyle.

It is concluded that the analysis of the state of dental health in terms of assessing the quality of life can help in solving many issues of organizing dental care for the elderly and senile population. By applying quality of life criteria, not only can oral health be improved, but the quality of care and well-being of older people can also be improved.

References:

1. Barsukov, V. N. (2014). Demograficheskoe starenie naseleniya: metody» ochenki [Demographic aging of the population: estimation methods]. *Voprosy territorialnogo razvitiya* [Issues of territorial development], 4 (14), 1-9. (In Russ.)
2. Atchison K. The General Oral Health Assessment Index (The Geriatric Oral Health Assessment Index). *Measuring Oral Health and Quality of Life*, 1997, pp. 72–80.
3. Borisova, E. G., Griga, E. S., Fedichkina, M. K., Sheenko, L. I. (2019). Izuchenie kachestva zhizni pacientov pri oslozhnennykh, vznikshix posle stomatologicheskix vmeshatel'stv [The study of the quality of life of patients with complications arising after dental interventions]. *Problemy stomatologii* [Problems of Dentistry], 15, 3, 23-27. (In Russ.)
4. Dumeev R. M., Bulgakov A. I., Islamov D. M. [Optimization of treatment and prevention for low-income persons with secondary edentulous]. *Kazanskii meditsinskii zhurnal = Kazan Medical Journal*, 2015, vol. 96, no. 4, pp. 549–553. (In Russ.)
5. Kamenev S. V., Salyamov Kh. Yu., Kitaev T. A., Danilina T. F. [The role of the orthopedic treatment of patients with complete absence of teeth in the assessment of the quality of life]. *Materialy Vserossiiskoi nauchno-prakticheskoj konferentsii, posvyashchennoi 50-letiyu stomatologicheskogo fakul'teta, Volgogradskogo gosudarstvennogo meditsinskogo universiteta «Stomatologiya – nauka i praktika. Perspektivy razvitiya»*. [«Dentistry – science and practice. Development prospects». Materials of All-Russian scientific-practical conference dedicated to the 50th anniversary of the Faculty of Dentistry, Volgograd State Medical University]. Volgograd, 2011, pp. 380–382.
6. Grover, V., Malhotra, R., Dhawan, S., Kaur, G. (2015). Comparative assessment of oral health related quality-of-life between rural and urban chronic periodontitis patients. *Saudi Journal of Oral Sciences*, 2, 1, 19.
7. Fedorova N. S., Saleev R. A. [Definition of the health concept within the life study of patients of dental profile]. *Vestnik sovremennoi klinicheskoi meditsiny = Herald of modern clinical medicine*, 2014, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 58–61. (In Russ.)
8. Shatrov I. M., Vedernikov L. V., Zholudev S. E. [A study using a questionnaire (OHIP-49) effects on the quality of life of patients with defects of hard dental tissue and dentition restored ceramic designs]. *Ural'skii meditsinskii zhurnal = Ural Medical Journal*, 2013, no. 5 (110), pp. 87–90. (In Russ.)
9. Stepanova, A. I., Nagaeva, M. O., Dzyuba, E. V. (2019). Dinamika kachestva zhizni bol'nykh s xronicheskim generalizovannym parodontitom srednej stepeni tyazhesti na fone tradicionnogo lecheniya [Dynamics of the quality of life of patients with chronic generalized periodontitis of moderate severity against the background of traditional treatment]. *Problemy stomatologii* [Problems of Dentistry], 15, 2, 32-36. (In Russ.)